

AN EVALUATION OF AFRICAN TRADITIONAL MEDICINE AS SOLUTION TO CONTEMPORARY PANDEMIC

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Abstract:

Traditional medicine is an aspect of African reality in which the African distinguished himself as against western orthodox medical practice. The question of this medical practice as a scientific enterprise has a philosophical over tone. The traditional medical practitioners are skilled practitioners who assist to improve health both within the confines of physical, mental and social wellbeing. The medical practice of the African is based on theories, beliefs and experiences that belongs to different peoples transmitted from generation to generation through training. This medical practice has been from thousands of years before modern orthodox medical practice. The application of local plants and mineral with medicinal properties accounts for its success. This paper evaluates the foundation, principles and justification for African traditional medicine as a scientific enterprise and solution to contemporary pandemic.